

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Hybridization of thermal and electrical storage simulations using TRNSYS simulation studio and validation from PROTEAS micro-grid data.
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	Hy Store
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Molten salt storage, battery storage, hybrid storage solutions and modelling.
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	18/12/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	12/01/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	19/12/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	11/01/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	8 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	During the public holidays and weekends the facility was closed
Number of days using the RI	15 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	One person
Comments	I arrived at 18 th of December late night and left at 12 th of January.
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>Collecting real-time operation and weather data: During my first week at PROTEAS, I was collecting the information from the components existing in the facility to create a simulation close enough to the real smart grid. List of the component details and see exactly how everything operates: After that I split the components into 5 smaller systems according to their location and type of input. The categories are Inverter PVs, PIKO PVs, Wind Turbine, Solar Dishes and Heliostats - Molten Salt system.</p>	

Create a simulation for each input:

I created a TRNSYS simulation for each of these systems and checked if they operate in logical values.

Put all the inputs in one, create the control logic:

The final step was to put all the systems into one TRNSYS simulation and connect them to get the final power output.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

With the valuable help from PROTEAS staff, I had to write down every single detail about the components. So, the first step was to measure the PIKO PVs dimensions and find out how they are connected with each other (four series with 10 PV each).

I did the same with the inverter PVs, a system of 459 PVs connected in 3 different blocks in different locations.

As a next step I had to find the scale details (high, power output according to the wind speed) for the Wind turbine from the company's webpage. Also, details about the geographical and altitude position of the Wind turbine had to be included.

For the Solar Dishes the information was limited, and we had to communicate with the company to give us the detail operation status (power output according to the weather data).

The Molten Salt – Heliostats system produce the bigger amount of power output in the facility but is the most complex also. I had to take us a count the reflectivity of the mirrors, the amount of the mirrors, the volume of the Molden salt and the efficiency of the steam turbine.

My project was to create a simulation, using TRNSYS simulation studios, which includes all of PROTEAS facility systems.

After that, I had to find out how and when the electric heaters are powered from the micro grid (inverter PVs, Wind Turbine and Solar Dishes) and calculate the output energy that PROTEAS facility can produce and store in thermal and electrical forms.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

I plotted the power production of each system and the overall power production to obtain data which I can compare with the real output which PROTEAS facility is collecting. I tried also to obtain other useful data like the temperature of the tank, the weather conditions, stage of charge of the batteries and when the electrical heaters are operated.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The results I got from the simulations are very promising and hopeful. According to the TRNSYS outputs, PROTEAS can produce enough electrical power for the needs of the facility during the winter months and during the summer months can even provide electricity to the public. Of course, the real data were showing lower production during my staying in the facility because of the unpredictable weather and other parameters which we cannot include to the simulations.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

I believe that the Simulations I created can help in the future for the prediction and of the power output according to the weather conditions and see if research facilities like PROTEAS can become industrial Power generation facilities and provide electrical power to the public.

Also, the most importance faction of my project, is that we can check if our components have a more efficient way to be connected or if the control system can improve.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

PROTEAS facility stuff was more than helpful, and they provided me with anything I asked. The only problems I come across was more small errors in the real data which they are expected when you are dealing with the real data.

Intended publications

My goal is finding a connection between the real data collected by PROTEAS and the simulation data collected by TRNSYS simulation studios, if I can achieve that, my publication will be about a yearly prediction of PROTEAS power output. The publication will be with the supervise of The Cyprus Institute.

Data management

As I mentioned my goal is for a yearly prediction. To achieve that I will have to visit again PROTEAS to collect data throughout the whole year.

Conclusions / additional comments

The research is promising good results and a useful output. I really want to finish the project to see what we can get.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1	2	3	4	5
	(excellent)		(neutral)		(poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1	2	3	4	5
	(excellent)		(neutral)		(poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Universities in general will help a lot I believe.					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
To achieve high TRL level we must increase the number of research happening is the thermal and mechanical energy storage systems.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

